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Statins are very effective against ovarian cancer

Research article

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Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

Several studies reported that statins inhibit the growth of a variety of cancer cell types. In this publication, the relationship between statin therapy and ovarian cancer has been re-investigated.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

New statistical methods were used.

RESULTS:

The marital status points to the possibility that ovarian cancer is a sexually transmitted disease, while human papillomavirus appears to be of causal importance in this context. A therapy with statins, which competitively inhibit 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme (HMG-CoA) reductase, is excluding ovarian cancer.

CONCLUSION:

Statins are protecting women against ovarian cancer (P Value = 0.0000092157).

Keywords:

Human papillomavirus; Ovarian cancer; Marital status; Statins; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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© Reviewer 3: None.

1. Introduction

Ovarian cancer (OC) is more or less the eighth leading cause of cancer-related death in women worldwide.¹ Unfortunately, OC has the highest mortality among gynaecological cancers and a poor prognosis. Despite indisputable achievements in the treatment of ovarian cancer, OC is still a severe condition with an unfavourable 5-year survival rate. Radical surgery and chemotherapy are not enough to manage this severe disease. The 5-year relative survival rates of the age group 15 – 44 years are higher than those of the other age groups and is decreasing with age.² The 5-year survival rates of the age group 65+ are more or less below 40%. New therapeutic options are urgently needed. Statins³ inhibit 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A (HMG-CoA) reductase. HMG-CoA reductase is an enzyme which activates the mevalonate pathway (MVP).⁴ Even if the mevalonate pathway mainly produces cholesterol, the mevalonate pathway also generates several other side products which are involved in tumour growth and metastasis. The mevalonate pathway is able to produce among other isoprenoids which are vital for diverse cellular functions, ranging from cholesterol synthesis to growth control. Long ago, the mevalonate pathway has been recognized as an excellent target of cancer therapeutics.⁵ Thus far, there are theoretical reasons to believe that statins may have the potential to reduce the risk of cancer. Meanwhile, several studies provided some slight evidence that statin medications may have anti-cancer properties too. In this publication, the relationship between a therapy with statins and ovarian cancer has been re-investigated.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

2.1.1. The study of Kato et al., 1989, Japan

What are the intrinsic properties of sex? Sex as a sweet temptation, is able to give new human life. At the same time, however, sex is also an intrinsically bad or undesirable destructive force of nature that ends human life en masse. Kato et al.⁶ investigated the relationship between marital status and cancer incidence based on 49,191 incident cases aged 30 or over in 1980–1984 by using the data from population-based Aichi Cancer Registry, Japan and census data.

¹Torre LA, Bray F, Siegel RL, Ferlay J, Lortet-Tieulent J, Jemal A. Global cancer statistics, 2012. *CA Cancer J Clin*. 2015 Mar;65(2):87-108. doi: 10.3322/caac.21262. Epub 2015 Feb 4. PMID: 25651787.

²Matsuda A, Katanoda K. Five-year relative survival rate of ovarian cancer in the USA, Europe and Japan. *Jpn J Clin Oncol*. 2014 Feb;44(2):196. doi: 10.1093/jjco/hyu007. PMID: 24496206.

³Endo A, Kuroda M, Tsujita Y. ML-236A, ML-236B, and ML-236C, new inhibitors of cholesterol synthesis produced by *Penicillium citrinum*. *J Antibiot (Tokyo)*. 1976 Dec;29(12):1346-8. doi: 10.7164/antibiotics.29.1346. PMID: 1010803.

⁴Wang CY, Liu PY, Liao JK. Pleiotropic effects of statin therapy: molecular mechanisms and clinical results. *Trends Mol Med*. 2008 Jan;14(1):37-44. doi: 10.1016/j.molmed.2007.11.004. PMID: 18068482; PMCID: PMC2621332.

⁵Goldstein JL, Brown MS. Regulation of the mevalonate pathway. *Nature*. 1990 Feb 1;343(6257):425-30. doi: 10.1038/343425a0. PMID: 1967820.

⁶Kato I, Tominaga S, Terao C. An epidemiological study on marital status and cancer incidence. *Jpn J Cancer Res*. 1989 Apr;80(4):306-11. doi: 10.1111/j.1349-7006.1989.tb02311.x. PMID: 2501246; PMCID: PMC5917738.

Table 1. Ever married and Cancer (Study of Kato et al., 1989, Japan).

		Cancer		
		YES	NO	
Ever married	YES	47712	3195359	3243071
	NO	1479	189090	190569
		49191	3384449	3433640
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.				
		Causal relationship k =	0,01339262	
		P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) =	0,00000000	
		p (SINE) =	0,99956926	
		p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) >	0,96993352	
		p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) >	0,99223903	
P VALUES.				
		P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) =	0,00000000	
		χ^2 (SINE— Not A _i) =	11,48	
		χ^2 (SINE— B _i) =	44,47	
		P Value (SINE) =	0,00043065	
PROPORTIONS.				
		(a/A) × 100 = (47712 / 3243071) × 100 =	1,47 %	
		(b/A) × 100 = (3195359 / 3243071) × 100 =	98,53 %	
		(c/ not A) × 100 = (1479 / 190569) × 100 =	0,78 %	
		(d/ not A) × 100 = (189090 / 190569) × 100 =	99,22 %	
		(a/B) × 100 = (47712 / 49191) × 100 =	96,99 %	
		(c/B) × 100 = (1479 / 49191) × 100 =	3,01 %	
		(b/ not B) × 100 = (3195359 / 3384449) × 100 =	94,41 %	
		(d/ not B) × 100 = (189090 / 3384449) × 100 =	5,59 %	
		(A/N) × 100 = (3243071 / 3433640) × 100 =	94,45 %	
		(not A/N) × 100 = (190569 / 3433640) × 100 =	5,55 %	
		(B/N) × 100 = (49191 / 3433640) × 100 =	1,43 %	
		(not B/N) × 100 = (3384449 / 3433640) × 100 =	98,57 %	
ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.				
RELATIVE RISK (RR).				
		RR (necessary condition) =	1,89563730	
		RR (sufficient condition) =	1,02733075	
OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.				
		Odds ratio (OR) =	1,90901065	
		Index of relationship (IOR) =	0,02692866	
STUDY DESIGN.				
		p(IOU)=	0,04117438	
		p(IOI)=	0,93017323	

The prevalence of cancer in the population investigated has been found to be $(B/N) \times 100 = (49191/3433640) \times 100 = 1.43\%$. The study design with $p(\text{IOU}) = 0.04117438$ has been impressive. However, the proportion of married, divorced or widowed with $((3195359/3433640) \times 100) = 93.06039655\%$ is too high. Thus far, the relationship between marital status and cancer is a little bit weaker than suggested by the data of Kato et al. However, the data published by Kato et al. are more or less of use. In general, the sexual behaviour at that time (1980-1984) in Japan may be considered confidently as rather not liberal, so that frequent extramarital sexual intercourse was rather the exception. The data of Kato et al. are in principle suitable as an indicator of the possibility of mutual infection during marital ⁷ intercourse as a cause of a wide variety of cancers. Following Kato et al., **without** being married **no** cancer ($p(\text{SINE}) = 1 - ((534+945)/((118811+70279)+(1461806+49963+28650)+(1345236)+(255137)+(54567))) = 0.9995630012$; P Value = 0.0004369987552). This finding should at least have consequences for the sexual education and the sexual life of people. The provisional use of two condoms on top of each other, with the second one being brought to use by the women, as a cheap and effective measure against ejaculatio praecox and mutual sexually transmitted infection (STI) is worth being considered.

⁷Ernst VL, Sacks ST, Selvin S, Petrakis NL. Cancer incidence by marital status: U.S. Third National Cancer Survey. J Natl Cancer Inst. 1979 Sep;63(3):567-85. doi: 10.1093/jnci/63.3.567. PMID: 288925.

2.1.2. The study of Fortner et al., 2019, USA (Fair study design)

Fortner et al. ⁸ provided data on the relationship between marital status and ovarian cancer. However, the study of Fortner et al. ⁹ has been highly unfair. The marital status (married, divorced or widowed) of the United States women in 2021 ¹⁰ has been about $((1 - ((41,81)/(136,84))) * 100) = 69.4\%$. Under conditions of fair study design it is $a = d = 327$ and about 30 %. Therefore, we obtain $b = 673$.

Table 2. Ever married and ovarian cancer (Study of Fortner et al. (Fair study design), 2019, USA).

		Ovarian cancer		
		YES	NO	
Ever married	YES	327	673	1000
	NO	10	327	337
		337	1000	1337

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship $k = 0,29732641$
 P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
p (SINE) = 0,99252057
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 0,97032641
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 0,97032641

P VALUES.
 P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 χ^2 (SINE— Not A_i) = 0,30
 χ^2 (SINE— B_i) = 0,30
 P Value (SINE) = **0,00745153**

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (327 / 1000) \times 100 = 32,70\%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (673 / 1000) \times 100 = 67,30\%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (10 / 337) \times 100 = 2,97\%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (327 / 337) \times 100 = 97,03\%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (327 / 337) \times 100 = 97,03\%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (10 / 337) \times 100 = 2,97\%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (673 / 1000) \times 100 = 67,30\%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (327 / 1000) \times 100 = 32,70\%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (1000 / 1337) \times 100 = 74,79\%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (337 / 1337) \times 100 = 25,21\%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (337 / 1337) \times 100 = 25,21\%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (1000 / 1337) \times 100 = 74,79\%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
 RR (necessary condition) = 11,01990000
 RR (sufficient condition) = 1,44179258

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
 Odds ratio (OR) = 15,88841010
 Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,29732641

STUDY DESIGN.
 p(IOU) = **0,00000000**
 p(IOI) = 0,49588631

⁸Fortner RT, Terry KL, Bender N, Brenner N, Hufnagel K, Butt J, Waterboer T, Tworoger SS. Sexually transmitted infections and risk of epithelial ovarian cancer: results from the Nurses' Health Studies. *Br J Cancer.* 2019 Apr;120(8):855-860. doi: 10.1038/s41416-019-0422-9. Epub 2019 Mar 21. PMID: 30894687; PMCID: PMC6474309.

⁹Fortner RT, Terry KL, Bender N, Brenner N, Hufnagel K, Butt J, Waterboer T, Tworoger SS. Sexually transmitted infections and risk of epithelial ovarian cancer: results from the Nurses' Health Studies. *Br J Cancer.* 2019 Apr;120(8):855-860. doi: 10.1038/s41416-019-0422-9. Epub 2019 Mar 21. PMID: 30894687; PMCID: PMC6474309.

¹⁰Marital status of the United States population in 2021, by sex

The marital status is a necessary condition of ovarian cancer (p (SINE) = 0.99252057). Only about $(c/B) \times 100 = (10 / 337) \times 100 = 2.97\%$ of cancers are not determined by the marital status. However, the marital status cannot be regarded as the cause of cancer. One aspect of the marital status is the sexual intercourse and mutual infection determined by the same. Singles or never married might become infected by themselves (self-infection) or might succumb to a sexually transmitted infection during extramarital sexual intercourse. The question is justified whether human papilloma virus (HPV) could have been causally related to ovarian carcinoma?

2.1.3. The study of Fortner et al., 2019, USA

Fortner et al. investigated (Nurses' Health Studies) whether sexually transmitted infections are related to pelvic inflammatory ¹¹, ¹² disease and tubal pathologies and their aetiology. Fortner et al. ¹³ provided data on the relationship HPV and OC. Cases and controls were matched 1:1. HPV infection with HPV types 16, 18, and 45 was assessed evaluating plasma samples HPV antibodies to the corresponding L1, E6, and E7 proteins (see table 3).

Table 3. Relationship: HPV and ovarian cancer (Study of Fortner et al. , 2019; USA).

		Ovarian cancer		
		YES	NO	
HPV	YES	11	7	18
	NO	326	330	656
		337	337	674

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship $k = +0,03681051$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,23731986
p (IMP) = 0,989614243
p (IMP) approx.= 1-(b/A) > 0,611111111
p (IMP) approx.= 1-(b/(Not B)) > 0,97922849
P VALUES.
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,88424281
 χ^2 (IMP— A_t) = 2,72
 χ^2 (IMP— Not B_t) = 0,15
P Value (IMP) = **0,01033201**

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/N) \times 100 = (11 / 674) \times 100 = 1,63 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (7 / 674) \times 100 = 1,04 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (326 / 674) \times 100 = 48,37 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (330 / 674) \times 100 = 48,96 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (11 / 18) \times 100 = 61,11 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (7 / 18) \times 100 = 38,89 \%$
 $(c/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (326 / 656) \times 100 = 49,70 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (330 / 656) \times 100 = 50,30 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (11 / 337) \times 100 = 3,26 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (326 / 337) \times 100 = 96,74 \%$
 $(b/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (7 / 337) \times 100 = 2,08 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (330 / 337) \times 100 = 97,92 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (18 / 674) \times 100 = 2,67 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (656 / 674) \times 100 = 97,33 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (337 / 674) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (337 / 674) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = 1,22972052
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,57142857

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = 1,59070990
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,22222222

STUDY DESIGN.
p(IOU)= **0,47329377**
p(IOI)= 0,47329377

¹¹Rosa MI, Silva GD, de Azedo Simões PW, Souza MV, Panatto AP, Simon CS, Madeira K, Medeiros LR. The prevalence of human papillomavirus in ovarian cancer: a systematic review. *Int J Gynecol Cancer.* 2013 Mar;23(3):437-41. doi: 10.1097/IGC.0b013e318280f3e0. PMID: 23354370.

¹²Cherif S, Amine A, Thies S, Taube ET, Braicu EI, Sehoul J, Kaufmann AM. Prevalence of human papillomavirus detection in ovarian cancer: a meta-analysis. *Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis.* 2021 Sep;40(9):1791-1802. doi: 10.1007/s10096-021-04282-7. Epub 2021 Jun 4. PMID: 34086102; PMCID: PMC8346400.

¹³Fortner RT, Terry KL, Bender N, Brenner N, Hufnagel K, Butt J, Waterboer T, Tworoger SS. Sexually transmitted infections and risk of epithelial ovarian cancer: results from the Nurses' Health Studies. *Br J Cancer.* 2019 Apr;120(8):855-860. doi: 10.1038/s41416-019-0422-9. Epub 2019 Mar 21. PMID: 30894687; PMCID: PMC6474309.

Fortner et al. provided some evidence (P Value = 0,01033201), that HPV is a sufficient condition of ovarian cancer (p(IMP) = 0,989614243; P Value = 0,01033201; Causal relationship > 0). However, the study design was not very convincing (p(IOU)= 0,47329377). In other words, it is difficult to rely on these data. These data have not been considered for the final conclusion drawn.

2.1.4. The study of Wu et al., 2003, China

Wu et al. ¹⁴ detected the presence of human papillomavirus-16 ¹⁵ (HPV-16) by in situ hybridisation (ISH) in (26/50) cases of ovarian cancer tissues and (2/30) controls.

Table 4. Relationship: HPV 16 (ISH) and ovarian cancer (Study of Wu et al., 2003).

		Ovarian cancer		
		YES	NO	
HPV 16 (ISH)	YES	26	2	28
	NO	24	28	52
		50	30	80

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,46013217$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00001931
 p (IMP) = 0,975
 p (IMP) approx.= $1-(b/A) > 0,92857143$
 p (IMP) approx.= $1-(b/(Not B)) > 0,93333333$

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,99999886
 χ^2 (IMP— A_i) = 0,14
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP— Not B_i) = 0,13
P Value (IMP) = **0,02469009**

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (26 / 80) \times 100 = 32,50 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (2 / 80) \times 100 = 2,50 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (24 / 80) \times 100 = 30,00 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (28 / 80) \times 100 = 35,00 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (26 / 28) \times 100 = 92,86 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (2 / 28) \times 100 = 7,14 \%$
 $(c/ not A) \times 100 = (24 / 52) \times 100 = 46,15 \%$
 $(d/ not A) \times 100 = (28 / 52) \times 100 = 53,85 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (26 / 50) \times 100 = 52,00 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (24 / 50) \times 100 = 48,00 \%$
 $(b/ not B) \times 100 = (2 / 30) \times 100 = 6,67 \%$
 $(d/ not B) \times 100 = (28 / 30) \times 100 = 93,33 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (28 / 80) \times 100 = 35,00 \%$
 $(not A/N) \times 100 = (52 / 80) \times 100 = 65,00 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (50 / 80) \times 100 = 62,50 \%$
 $(not B/N) \times 100 = (30 / 80) \times 100 = 37,50 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 2,01190476
RR (sufficient condition) = 7,80000000

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 15,16666667
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,48571429

STUDY DESIGN.

p (IOU)= **0,02500000**
 p (IOI)= 0,27500000

Within the possibilities that the ISH methodology provides, Wu et al. were able to present a very convincing proof of the sufficient condition relationship between HPV and OC (p (IMP) = 0,975; P Value (IMP) = 0,02469009) while the study design has been very impressive (p (IOU)= 0,025). In other words, if HPV within ovarian tissues (detected by ISH), then ovarian cancer. However, even the ISH methodology is not without errors.

¹⁴Wu QJ, Guo M, Lu ZM, Li T, Qiao HZ, Ke Y. Detection of human papillomavirus-16 in ovarian malignancy. Br J Cancer. 2003 Aug 18;89(4):672-5. doi: 10.1038/sj.bjc.6601172. PMID: 12915876; PMCID: PMC2376933.

¹⁵zur Hausen H. Papillomaviruses in human cancers. Proc Assoc Am Physicians. 1999 Nov-Dec;111(6):581-7. doi: 10.1046/j.1525-1381.1999.99723.x. PMID: 10591087.

In situ hybridization

In situ hybridization ¹⁶ (ISH) is a methodology which is used to localize or detect specific DNA and RNA nucleotide sequences in cells, in tissue sections, and even whole tissue. Meanwhile, many different ISH methods have been developed. Depending on the probe used, different methods (fluorescence microscopy, autoradiography, or immunohistochemistry) are used for visualization. However, advantages and disadvantages ¹⁷ of the extensively used in situ hybridization need to be considered too, the specificity and sensitivity of ISH depend on the target used, too. In fact, a major disadvantage ¹⁸ of the in situ hybridization methodology are targets that have low DNA and RNA copies. Under these conditions, the in situ hybridization might reach its own limits. False negative ISH results are possible, but false positive ISH results too. Nonetheless, In-situ hybridization is able to distinguish virus in tumour cells from virus in other cells than tumour cells, i.e. such cells as lymphocytes. ¹⁹ , ²⁰ , ²¹ , ²²

¹⁶Gall JG, Pardue ML. Formation and detection of RNA-DNA hybrid molecules in cytological preparations. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 1969 Jun;63(2):378-83. doi: 10.1073/pnas.63.2.378. PMID: 4895535; PMCID: PMC223575.

¹⁷Jensen E. Technical review: In situ hybridization. *Anat Rec (Hoboken)*. 2014 Aug;297(8):1349-53. doi: 10.1002/ar.22944. Epub 2014 May 9. PMID: 24810158.

¹⁸Qian X, Lloyd RV. Recent developments in signal amplification methods for in situ hybridization. *Diagn Mol Pathol*. 2003 Mar;12(1):1-13. doi: 10.1097/00019606-200303000-00001. PMID: 12605030.

¹⁹Richardson AK, Currie MJ, Robinson BA, Morrin H, Phung Y, Pearson JF, Anderson TP, Potter JD, Walker LC. Cytomegalovirus and Epstein-Barr virus in breast cancer. *PLoS One*. 2015 Feb 27;10(2):e0118989. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0118989. PMID: 25723522; PMCID: PMC4344231.

²⁰Cox B, Richardson A, Graham P, Gislefoss RE, Jellum E, Rollag H. Breast cancer, cytomegalovirus and Epstein-Barr virus: a nested case-control study. *Br J Cancer*. 2010 May 25;102(11):1665-9. doi: 10.1038/sj.bjc.6605675. Epub 2010 Apr 20. PMID: 20407437; PMCID: PMC2883146.

²¹Richardson AK, Cox B, McCredie MR, Dite GS, Chang JH, Gertig DM, Southey MC, Giles GG, Hopper JL. Cytomegalovirus, Epstein-Barr virus and risk of breast cancer before age 40 years: a case-control study. *Br J Cancer*. 2004 Jun 1;90(11):2149-52. doi: 10.1038/sj.bjc.6601822. PMID: 15150559; PMCID: PMC2409506.

²²Info: EBV IgG and breast cancer and case control study

2.1.5. The study of Kuscu et al., 2005, Turkey

The causal importance of HPV infection in ovarian cancer is still unsure and under studies. Kuscu et al. ²³ examined the presence of human papillomavirus (HPV) in ovarian cancer tissues by in situ hybridization and immunohistochemistry (IHC). In toto, (15/40) cases of ovarian cancer embedded in paraffin blocks and (9/32) controls were positive for HPV.

Table 5. Relationship: HPV (ISH) and ovarian cancer (Study of Kuscu et al., 2005).

		Ovarian cancer		
		YES	NO	
HPV (ISH)	YES	15	9	24
	NO	25	23	48
		40	32	72

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship k = 0,09882118
 P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,27959822
p (IMP) = 0,875
p (IMP) approx.= 1-(b/A) > 0,62500000
p (IMP) approx.= 1-(b/(Not B)) > 0,71875000
P VALUES.
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,86231820
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP— A_t) = 3,38
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP— Not B_t) = 2,53
 P Value (IMP) = 0,11750310
PROPORTIONS.
 (a/N) × 100 = (15 / 72) × 100 = 20,83 %
 (b/N) × 100 = (9 / 72) × 100 = 12,50 %
 (c/N) × 100 = (25 / 72) × 100 = 34,72 %
 (d/N) × 100 = (23 / 72) × 100 = 31,94 %
 (a/A) × 100 = (15 / 24) × 100 = 62,50 %
 (b/A) × 100 = (9 / 24) × 100 = 37,50 %
 (c/ not A) × 100 = (25 / 48) × 100 = 52,08 %
 (d/ not A) × 100 = (23 / 48) × 100 = 47,92 %
 (a/B) × 100 = (15 / 40) × 100 = 37,50 %
 (c/B) × 100 = (25 / 40) × 100 = 62,50 %
 (b/ not B) × 100 = (9 / 32) × 100 = 28,13 %
 (d/ not B) × 100 = (23 / 32) × 100 = 71,88 %
 (A/N) × 100 = (24 / 72) × 100 = 33,33 %
 (not A/N) × 100 = (48 / 72) × 100 = 66,67 %
 (B/N) × 100 = (40 / 72) × 100 = 55,56 %
 (not B/N) × 100 = (32 / 72) × 100 = 44,44 %
ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
 RR (necessary condition) = 1,20000000
 RR (sufficient condition) = 1,33333333
OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
 Odds ratio (OR) = 1,53333333
 Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,12500000
STUDY DESIGN.
 p(IOU)= 0,11111111
 p(IOI)= 0,22222222

The study design has been unfair (p(IOU)= 0,11111111). Still, Kuscu at al. provided some, even if restricted evidence, that HPV is a sufficient condition of OC (p (IMP) = 0,875; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP— A_t) = 3,38; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP— Not B_t) = 2,53).

²³Kuscu E, Ozdemir BH, Erkanli S, Haberal A. HPV and p53 expression in epithelial ovarian carcinoma. Eur J Gynaecol Oncol. 2005;26(6):642-5. PMID: 16398227.

2.1.6. The study of Paradowska et al., 2019, Poland

Paradowska et al. ²⁴ examined the prevalence of human papillomavirus in OC tissue and fallopian tube specimens obtained at tumour resection by PCR and quantitative real-time PCR (qRT-PCR).

Table 6. Relationship: HPV (PCR) and ovarian cancer (Study of Paradowska et al.,2019).

		Ovarian cancer		
		YES	NO	
HPV (PCR)	YES	22	2	24
	NO	5	6	11
		27	8	35

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,51089422$
 P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00576130
 p (IMP) = 0,942857143
 p (IMP) approx.= $1-(b/A)$ > 0,91666667
 p (IMP) approx.= $1-(b/(Not B))$ > 0,75000000

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,99965648
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP— A_t) = 0,17
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP— Not B_t) = 0,50
 P Value (IMP) = 0,05554086

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (22 / 35) \times 100 = 62,86 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (2 / 35) \times 100 = 5,71 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (5 / 35) \times 100 = 14,29 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (6 / 35) \times 100 = 17,14 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (22 / 24) \times 100 = 91,67 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (2 / 24) \times 100 = 8,33 \%$
 $(c/ not A) \times 100 = (5 / 11) \times 100 = 45,45 \%$
 $(d/ not A) \times 100 = (6 / 11) \times 100 = 54,55 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (22 / 27) \times 100 = 81,48 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (5 / 27) \times 100 = 18,52 \%$
 $(b/ not B) \times 100 = (2 / 8) \times 100 = 25,00 \%$
 $(d/ not B) \times 100 = (6 / 8) \times 100 = 75,00 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (24 / 35) \times 100 = 68,57 \%$
 $(not A/N) \times 100 = (11 / 35) \times 100 = 31,43 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (27 / 35) \times 100 = 77,14 \%$
 $(not B/N) \times 100 = (8 / 35) \times 100 = 22,86 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 2,01666667
 RR (sufficient condition) = 3,25925926

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 13,20000000
 Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,18827160

STUDY DESIGN.

p (IOU)= 0,45714286
 p (IOI)= 0,08571429

Paradowska et al. confirmed the common presence of HPV16 in 70% of OC cases. The study design with p (IOI)= +0,08571429 has been appropriate enough to demonstrate even a cause effect relationship between HPV and OC (Causal relationship $k = +0,51089422$; P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00576130) while the sufficient condition relationship has been significant (p (IMP) = 0,942857143; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP— A_t) = 0,17; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP— Not B_t) = 0,50).

²⁴Paradowska E, Jabłońska A, Studzińska M, Wilczyński M, Wilczyński JR. Detection and genotyping of CMV and HPV in tumors and fallopian tubes from epithelial ovarian cancer patients. Sci Rep. 2019 Dec 27;9(1):19935. doi: 10.1038/s41598-019-56448-1. PMID: 31882737; PMCID: PMC6934444.

2.1.1.7. The study of Shokouh et al., 2020, Iran

Mohammad Reza Shokouh et al. ²⁵ evaluated in a case-control study the frequency of HPV deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) inside 205 Paraffin-embedded ovarian tissue specimens including 68 malignant OC and 45 normal tissues. The β -globin gene has been amplified by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) to confirm the quality of the extracted DNA. HPV genome (genotypes 16 and 18) has been identified using specific primers by PCR. “In detail, 13 (19.1%) samples of malignant group (3 with grade I, 3 with grade II and 7 with grade III), 6 (22.2%) samples of borderline tumour, 3 (4.6%) samples of benign group and none (0%) of the control group had positive result for HPV.”. Shokouh et al. pointed to a possible role of high risk HPVs in the pathogenesis of ovarian cancer (see table 7).

Table 7. Relationship: HPV PCR DNA and ovarian cancer (Study of Shokouh et al., 2020).

		Ovarian cancer		
		YES	NO	
HPV PCR DNA	YES	13	0	13
	NO	55	45	100
		68	45	113
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.				
		Causal relationship $k = +0,29330771$		
		P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00081704		
		p (IMP) = 1		
		p (IMP) approx.= 1-(b/A) > 1,00000000		
		p (IMP) approx.= 1-(b/(Not B)) > 1,00000000		
P VALUES.				
		P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 1,00000000		
		χ^2 (IMP— A _t) = 0,00		
		χ^2 (IMP— Not B _t) = 0,00		
		P Value (IMP) = 0,00000000		
PROPORTIONS.				
		$(a/N) \times 100 = (13 / 113) \times 100 = 11,50 \%$		
		$(b/N) \times 100 = (0 / 113) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$		
		$(c/N) \times 100 = (55 / 113) \times 100 = 48,67 \%$		
		$(d/N) \times 100 = (45 / 113) \times 100 = 39,82 \%$		
		$(a/A) \times 100 = (13 / 13) \times 100 = 100,00 \%$		
		$(b/A) \times 100 = (0 / 13) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$		
		$(c/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (55 / 100) \times 100 = 55,00 \%$		
		$(d/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (45 / 100) \times 100 = 45,00 \%$		
		$(a/B) \times 100 = (13 / 68) \times 100 = 19,12 \%$		
		$(c/B) \times 100 = (55 / 68) \times 100 = 80,88 \%$		
		$(b/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (0 / 45) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$		
		$(d/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (45 / 45) \times 100 = 100,00 \%$		
		$(A/N) \times 100 = (13 / 113) \times 100 = 11,50 \%$		
		$(\text{not A}/N) \times 100 = (100 / 113) \times 100 = 88,50 \%$		
		$(B/N) \times 100 = (68 / 113) \times 100 = 60,18 \%$		
		$(\text{not B}/N) \times 100 = (45 / 113) \times 100 = 39,82 \%$		
ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.				
RELATIVE RISK (RR).				
		RR (necessary condition) = 1,81818182		
		RR (sufficient condition) = Division by zero!		
OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.				
		Odds ratio (OR) = Division by zero!		
		Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,66176471		
STUDY DESIGN.				
		p(IOU)= 0,28318584		
		p(IOI)= 0,48672566		

²⁵Shokouh MR, Safaei A, Moattari A, Sarvari J. Association of Human Papilloma Virus and Epstein-Barr Virus with Ovarian Cancer in Shiraz, Southwestern Iran. Iran J Pathol. 2020 Fall;15(4):292-298. doi: 10.30699/ijp.2020.119681.2306. Epub 2020 Jul 16. PMID: 32944041; PMCID: PMC7477684.

The study design of the study of Shokouh et al. has been very unfair ($p(\text{IOU})=0,28318584$). Still, Shokouh et al. were able to provide highly significant statistical evidence, that HPV is a sufficient condition of ovarian cancer. In other words, **if** HPV DNA present in ovarian tissues, **then** ovarian cancer ($p(\text{IMP}) = 1$; P Value = 0; Causal relationship > 0). Other study groups examined the presence of human papilloma virus types 16, 18 in upper genital tract of women too²⁶ and found what they were looking for. Even statins themselves, competitive inhibitors of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-coenzyme A (HMG-CoA) reductase, which have anti-tumoral effects on multiple cancer types, may also provide additional (indirect) evidence of OC pathology. Statins inhibit the proliferation and induce cell death of cervical cancer (cells)²⁷ which itself is caused by human papilloma virus^{28, 29} and do inhibit the metastatic potential and invasive properties of the tumor cells.³⁰ Efficacy of statins against OC would be another, albeit very weak, evidence for HPV as a cause of OC.

²⁶Bilyk OO, Pande NT, Pejovic T, Buchinska LG. The frequency of human papilloma virus types 16, 18 in upper genital tract of women at high risk of developing ovarian cancer. *Exp Oncol*. 2014 Jun;36(2):121-4. PMID: 24980768.

²⁷Crescencio ME, Rodríguez E, Páez A, Masso FA, Montaña LF, López-Marure R. Statins inhibit the proliferation and induce cell death of human papilloma virus positive and negative cervical cancer cells. *Int J Biomed Sci*. 2009 Dec;5(4):411-20. PMID: 23675166; PMCID: PMC3614803.

²⁸Barukčić, I. (2018) Human Papillomavirus—The Cause of Human Cervical Cancer. *Journal of Biosciences and Medicines*, 6, 106-125. doi: 10.4236/jbm.2018.64009.

²⁹Barukčić, Ilija. (2022). Human papillomavirus is the cause of human invasive cervical cancer. *Causation*, 17(4), 67–139. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6465170>

³⁰Castelazo Rico G, Molotla Xolalpa D, Basavilvazo Rodríguez MA, Angeles Victoria L, Zárate A, Hernández Valencia M. Supervivencia de pacientes con cáncer de mama tratadas con inhibidores de la aromatización vs tamoxifeno [Survival of breast cancer patients treated with inhibitors of the aromatase vs tamoxifen]. *Ginecol Obstet Mex*. 2004 Oct;72:493-9. Spanish. PMID: 15790189. [Article in Spanish]

2.1.8. The study of Baandrup et al., 2015, Denmark

Statin (3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme, a reductase inhibitor) extensively used for treatment of hypercholesterolemia and prevention of cardiovascular disease has been suggested to be associated with a lower risk of ovaries cancer too. ³¹ Baandrup et al. ³² investigated the relationship between ever use of statins and ovarian cancer and identified 4103 cases of epithelial ovarian cancer and 58,706 age-matched controls (see table 8).

Table 8. Relationship: Ever use of statins and ovarian cancer (Study of Baandrup et al., 2022; Denmark).

		Ovarian cancer		
		YES	NO	
Ever use of statins	YES	434	6445	6879
	NO	3669	52261	55930
		4103	58706	62809

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship $k = -0,00317135$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,22167382
p (EXCL) = 0,99309016
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,93690943
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,89422374

P VALUES.
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,22167382
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_r) = 27,38130542
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_r) = 45,90689739
P Value (EXCL) = **0,00688602**

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/N) \times 100 = (434 / 62809) \times 100 = 0,69 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (6445 / 62809) \times 100 = 10,26 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (3669 / 62809) \times 100 = 5,84 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (52261 / 62809) \times 100 = 83,21 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (434 / 6879) \times 100 = 6,31 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (6445 / 6879) \times 100 = 93,69 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (3669 / 55930) \times 100 = 6,56 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (52261 / 55930) \times 100 = 93,44 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (434 / 4103) \times 100 = 10,58 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (3669 / 4103) \times 100 = 89,42 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (6445 / 58706) \times 100 = 10,98 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (52261 / 58706) \times 100 = 89,02 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (6879 / 62809) \times 100 = 10,95 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (55930 / 62809) \times 100 = 89,05 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (4103 / 62809) \times 100 = 6,53 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (58706 / 62809) \times 100 = 93,47 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = 0,96174852
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,96349126

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = 0,95917271
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,03420538

STUDY DESIGN.
p(IOU) = 0,82515245
p(IOI) = 0,04419749

The study design has been fair (p(IOI)= 0,04419749). Ever use of statins excludes ovarian cancer (p (EXCL) = 0,99309016; P Value (EXCL) = 0,0068860; Causal relationship $k = -0,00317135$).

³¹Stryjowska-Góra A, Karczmarek-Borowska B, Góra T, Krawczak K. Statins and cancers. *Contemp Oncol (Pozn)*. 2015;19(3):167-75. doi: 10.5114/wo.2014.44294. Epub 2014 Aug 29. PMID: 26557755; PMCID: PMC4631290.

³²Baandrup L, Dehlendorff C, Friis S, Olsen JH, Kjær SK. Statin use and risk for ovarian cancer: a Danish nationwide case-control study. *Br J Cancer*. 2015 Jan 6;112(1):157-61. doi: 10.1038/bjc.2014.574. Epub 2014 Nov 13. PMID: 25393364; PMCID: PMC4453615.

2.1.9. The study of Akinwunmi et al., 2019, USA

Cholesterol as a steroid precursor is of great significance for cellular homeostasis and for biologic function of cell membranes. Therefore, lowering cholesterol might also have impact on cancer. ³³ Meanwhile, Liu et al. ³⁴ provided some evidence that statins can induce apoptosis in ovarian cancer cell lines. Akinwunmi et al. ³⁵ investigated in a population-based case-control study (see table 9)

Table 9. Relationship: statin therapy > 6 month and ovarian cancer (Study of Akinwunmi et al., 2019; USA).

		Ovarian cancer		
		YES	NO	
Statin therapy	YES	188	245	433
	NO	1852	1855	3707
		2040	2100	4140

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship k = -0,04004141
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00572351
p (EXCL) = 0,95458937
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,56581986
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,90784314

P VALUES.
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00572351
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_t) = 81,62586605
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_t) = 17,32549020
P Value (EXCL) = **0,04439500**

PROPORTIONS.
(a/N) × 100 = (188 / 4140) × 100 = 4,54 %
(b/N) × 100 = (245 / 4140) × 100 = 5,92 %
(c/N) × 100 = (1852 / 4140) × 100 = 44,73 %
(d/N) × 100 = (1855 / 4140) × 100 = 44,81 %
(a/A) × 100 = (188 / 433) × 100 = 43,42 %
(b/A) × 100 = (245 / 433) × 100 = 56,58 %
(c/ not A) × 100 = (1852 / 3707) × 100 = 49,96 %
(d/ not A) × 100 = (1855 / 3707) × 100 = 50,04 %
(a/B) × 100 = (188 / 2040) × 100 = 9,22 %
(c/B) × 100 = (1852 / 2040) × 100 = 90,78 %
(b/ not B) × 100 = (245 / 2100) × 100 = 11,67 %
(d/ not B) × 100 = (1855 / 2100) × 100 = 88,33 %
(A/N) × 100 = (433 / 4140) × 100 = 10,46 %
(not A/N) × 100 = (3707 / 4140) × 100 = 89,54 %
(B/N) × 100 = (2040 / 4140) × 100 = 49,28 %
(not B/N) × 100 = (2100 / 4140) × 100 = 50,72 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = 0,86906359
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,78991597

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = 0,76858994
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,11886972

STUDY DESIGN.
p(IOU)= 0,40265700
p(IOI)= 0,38816425

³³Dulak J, Józkwicz A. Anti-angiogenic and anti-inflammatory effects of statins: relevance to anti-cancer therapy. *Curr Cancer Drug Targets*. 2005 Dec;5(8):579-94. doi: 10.2174/156800905774932824. PMID: 16375664; PMCID: PMC1391922.

³⁴Liu H, Liang SL, Kumar S, Weyman CM, Liu W, Zhou A. Statins induce apoptosis in ovarian cancer cells through activation of JNK and enhancement of Bim expression. *Cancer Chemother Pharmacol*. 2009 May;63(6):997-1005. doi: 10.1007/s00280-008-0830-7. Epub 2008 Sep 3. PMID: 18766339.

³⁵Akinwunmi B, Vitonis AF, Titus L, Terry KL, Cramer DW. Statin therapy and association with ovarian cancer risk in the New England Case Control (NEC) study. *Int J Cancer*. 2019 Mar 1;144(5):991-1000. doi: 10.1002/ijc.31758. Epub 2018 Oct 30. PMID: 30006925; PMCID: PMC6320710.

the relationship between statin therapy and ovarian cancer risk in the New England Case Control (NEC) Study and observed a 32% lower risk of ovarian cancer for statin users compared to non-users.³⁶,³⁷ The impact of predominantly lipophilic (fat) statins (simvastatin, fluvastatin, pitavastatin, lovastatin and atorvastatin)³⁸ or hydrophilic (water) statins (rosuvastatin and pravastatin) on ovarian cancer has been considered too. According to Akinwunmi et al., statin therapy over more than 6 months excludes ovarian cancer (p (EXCL) = 0,95458937; P Value (EXCL) = 0,04439500; Causal relationship $k < 0$). However, the study design has been very unfair (p (IOI)= 0,38816425).

³⁶Graaf MR, Beiderbeck AB, Egberts AC, Richel DJ, Guchelaar HJ. The risk of cancer in users of statins. *J Clin Oncol*. 2004 Jun 15;22(12):2388-94. doi: 10.1200/JCO.2004.02.027. PMID: 15197200.

³⁷Liu Y, Qin A, Li T, Qin X, Li S. Effect of statin on risk of gynecologic cancers: a meta-analysis of observational studies and randomized controlled trials. *Gynecol Oncol*. 2014 Jun;133(3):647-55. doi: 10.1016/j.ygyno.2014.04.007. Epub 2014 Apr 13. PMID: 24736024.

³⁸Climent E, Benaiges D, Pedro-Botet J. Hydrophilic or Lipophilic Statins? *Front Cardiovasc Med*. 2021 May 20;8:687585. doi: 10.3389/fcvm.2021.687585. PMID: 34095267; PMCID: PMC8172607.

2.1.10. The study of Akinwunmi et al., 2019, USA

The proportion of statin users of the study of Akinwunmi et al. with $(A/N) \times 100 = (2040 / 8702) \times 100 = 23,44\%$ is grossly underestimated. In contrast to the study of Akinwunmi et al., the proportion of statin use increased from 14.9% in 1999 to 2000 to 27.8% in 2017 to 2018.³⁹ Under fair study conditions, it should be $B = A = 2040$ while $2040/N = 0.278$, and $N = 7338$. We should obtain a more realistic picture as follows (see table 10).

Table 10. Relationship: statin therapy > 6 month and ovarian cancer (Study of Akinwunmi et al. (Fair study design I) , 2019).

		Ovarian cancer		
		YES	NO	
Statin therapy	YES	188	1852	2040
	NO	1852	3446	5298
		2040	5298	7338

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship $k = -0,25740901$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
p (EXCL) = 0,97437994
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,90784314
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,90784314

P VALUES.
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_t) = 17,32549020
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_t) = 17,32549020
P Value (EXCL) = **0,02529465**

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/N) \times 100 = (188 / 7338) \times 100 = 2,56\%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (1852 / 7338) \times 100 = 25,24\%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (1852 / 7338) \times 100 = 25,24\%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (3446 / 7338) \times 100 = 46,96\%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (188 / 2040) \times 100 = 9,22\%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (1852 / 2040) \times 100 = 90,78\%$
 $(c/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (1852 / 5298) \times 100 = 34,96\%$
 $(d/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (3446 / 5298) \times 100 = 65,04\%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (188 / 2040) \times 100 = 9,22\%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (1852 / 2040) \times 100 = 90,78\%$
 $(b/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (1852 / 5298) \times 100 = 34,96\%$
 $(d/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (3446 / 5298) \times 100 = 65,04\%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (2040 / 7338) \times 100 = 27,80\%$
 $(\text{not A}/N) \times 100 = (5298 / 7338) \times 100 = 72,20\%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (2040 / 7338) \times 100 = 27,80\%$
 $(\text{not B}/N) \times 100 = (5298 / 7338) \times 100 = 72,20\%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = 0,26363232
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,26363232

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = 0,18888225
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,66850634

STUDY DESIGN.
p(IOU) = 0,44399019
p(IOI) = 0,00000000

³⁹Gao Y, Shah LM, Ding J, Martin SS. US Trends in Cholesterol Screening, Lipid Levels, and Lipid-Lowering Medication Use in US Adults, 1999 to 2018. J Am Heart Assoc. 2023 Feb 7;12(3):e028205. doi: 10.1161/JAHA.122.028205. Epub 2023 Jan 10. PMID: 36625302; PMCID: PMC9973640.

2.1.11. The study of Akinwunmi et al., 2019, USA

The proportion of a particular population found to be affected by ovarian carcinoma at a specific time (prevalence) varies and is about 10 per 100,000 women or 1 per 10,000 women⁴⁰ while the the proportion of statin use (A/N) is kept at 27.8%.⁴¹ As a consequence, 2040 cases of ovarian cancer assume a population of about 20,402,040 participants. Table 11 illustrates the consequences of this train of thought.

Table 11. Relationship: statin therapy > 6 month and ovarian cancer (Study of Akinwunmi et al. (Population), 2019).

		Ovarian cancer		
		YES	NO	
Statin therapy	YES	188	5671200	5671388
	NO	1852	14728800	14730652
		2040	20400000	20402040

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship k = -0,00414783

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000

p (EXCL) = 0,99999079

p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,99996685

p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,90784314

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_t) = 0,00623198

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_t) = 17,32549020

P Value (EXCL) = **0,00000921**

PROPORTIONS.

(a/N) × 100 = (188 / 20402040) × 100 = 0,00 %

(b/N) × 100 = (5671200 / 20402040) × 100 = 27,80 %

(c/N) × 100 = (1852 / 20402040) × 100 = 0,01 %

(d/N) × 100 = (14728800 / 20402040) × 100 = 72,19 %

(a/A) × 100 = (188 / 5671388) × 100 = 0,00 %

(b/A) × 100 = (5671200 / 5671388) × 100 = 100,00 %

(c/ not A) × 100 = (1852 / 14730652) × 100 = 0,01 %

(d/ not A) × 100 = (14728800 / 14730652) × 100 = 99,99 %

(a/B) × 100 = (188 / 2040) × 100 = 9,22 %

(c/B) × 100 = (1852 / 2040) × 100 = 90,78 %

(b/ not B) × 100 = (5671200 / 20400000) × 100 = 27,80 %

(d/ not B) × 100 = (14728800 / 20400000) × 100 = 72,20 %

(A/N) × 100 = (5671388 / 20402040) × 100 = 27,80 %

(not A/N) × 100 = (14730652 / 20402040) × 100 = 72,20 %

(B/N) × 100 = (2040 / 20402040) × 100 = 0,01 %

(not B/N) × 100 = (20400000 / 20402040) × 100 = 99,99 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 0,26366317

RR (sufficient condition) = 0,33149951

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,26363877

Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,66847833

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,72191859

p(IOI)= 0,27788143

Several aspects like original data (see table 9), fair study design I data (see table 10), fictive data (see table 11) et cetera can be considered with respect to the study of Akinwunmi et al., 2019, USA.

⁴⁰Gaona-Luviano P, Medina-Gaona LA, Magaña-Pérez K. Epidemiology of ovarian cancer. *Chin Clin Oncol.* 2020 Aug;9(4):47. doi: 10.21037/cco-20-34. Epub 2020 Jun 30. PMID: 32648448.

⁴¹Gao Y, Shah LM, Ding J, Martin SS. US Trends in Cholesterol Screening, Lipid Levels, and Lipid-Lowering Medication Use in US Adults, 1999 to 2018. *J Am Heart Assoc.* 2023 Feb 7;12(3):e028205. doi: 10.1161/JAHA.122.028205. Epub 2023 Jan 10. PMID: 36625302; PMCID: PMC9973640.

In the end, which study can we rely on, after all, each study has its advantages and disadvantages. An extreme disadvantage of the original data (see table 9) is the claim that $(B/N) \times 100 = (2040 / 4140) \times 100 = 49,28\%$ of a population are suffering from ovarian cancer. This is too far away from reality. However, even under these very unfavorable assumptions of Akinwunmi et al. we rightfully expect that statins should protect women against ovarian cancer with the consequence that $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{0}$. However, Akinwunmi et al. found that $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{188}$. This is a fact that cannot simply be ignored. Nonetheless, some questions arise in this regard. Foremost, where people work, mistakes are made. In other words, were the cases identified as ovarian cancer correctly diagnosed and identified as such? Furthermore, are pathology reports free of any error? In particular, the participants were asked whether they used statins for at least six consecutive months prior to their reference date. Was this really so ensured? Is there any difference between the statins used with respect to the protection against ovarian cancer? And by far the more important question is, are 6 months of statin therapy enough to protect women against ovarian cancer? All these and other objections justify the acceptance or rejection of a hypothesis while considering a certain level of significance or P Value. Against this background, we may therefore come to the following conclusion. **An appropriate therapy with statins is protecting women against ovarian cancer ($p(\text{EXCL}) = 1 - \frac{188}{20400000} = 0.9999907843$; P Value = 0.0000092157).**

2.2. Methods

Avoiding and treatment of logical fallacies addresses one of the most important aspects of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to something unknown**. It also goes without any need of further saying that a definition as such should be logically consistent and correct. However, theoretically, circumstances might exist under which it is required to *deal with erroneous definitions*⁴² too.

2.2.1. Conditio sine qua non relationship

The probability of the necessary condition relationship $p(\text{SINE})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B)$ and $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | \underline{A})$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019c). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, right-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided right-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a negative causal relationship ($k < 0$) would contradict a necessary condition relationship and vice versa.

2.2.2. Conditio per quam relationship

The probability of the sufficient condition relationship $p(\text{IMP})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b, 2022) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | A)$ and $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | \underline{B})$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of an sufficient condition relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019c). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, right-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided right-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a negative causal relationship would contradict a sufficient condition relationship and vice versa.

2.2.3. Exclusion relationship

The probability of the exclusion relationship $p(\text{EXCL})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | A)$ and

⁴²Strobino, Riccardo, "Ibn Sina's Logic", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

$\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | B)$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of an exclusion relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019c). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, left-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided left-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a positive causal relationship would contradict an exclusion relationship and vice versa.

2.2.4. Hyper-geometric distribution

In general, the probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable X is called a hyper-geometric distribution. In contrast to the binomial distribution, the hyper-geometric distribution is characterized by the lack of replacements. In this context, let N denote the population size, let A denote the number of success in the population, let B denote the number of draws (i.e. quantity drawn in each trial), let a itself denote the number of observed successes.

Table 12. Hyper-geometric random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	a	b	A
	FALSE	c	d	\underline{A}
		B	\underline{B}	N

With this in mind, the probability mass function of the hyper-geometric distribution (see Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899), denoted as $p(X = a)$, is defined as

$$p(X = a) = \frac{\binom{A}{a} \binom{N-A}{B-a}}{\binom{N}{B}} = \frac{\binom{B}{a} \binom{N-B}{A-a}}{\binom{N}{A}} \quad (1)$$

The hyper-geometric distribution, a probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable, has several properties which unfortunately cannot be discussed in detail here. A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some speci-

fied lower limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (2)$$

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is less than or equal to some specified upper limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (3)$$

2.2.5. Fisher's exact test

Fisher's exact test proposed by Fisher (1934) in the fifth edition of *Statistical Methods for Research Workers* (see Fisher, 1934, pp. 99-103) is a statistical significance test which is often used in the analysis of contingency tables while applying the hyper-geometric distribution⁴³. This statistical methodology opens up the possibility to calculate the significance of the deviation from a null hypothesis (e.g., P Value) exactly. Strangely enough, it is common practice to use Fisher's exact test (see also Fisher, 1935) for a sample which is very small. However, it is necessary to point out that Fisher's exact test is valid for all sample sizes without any restriction. Fisher's Exact Test is using the following null and alternative hypotheses:

H0: (null hypothesis)

The two random variables are independent.

H1: (alternative hypothesis)

The two random variables are not independent.

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability denotes whether a hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit and less than or equal to some specified upper limit. The P Value of an one-sided right tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (4)$$

The P Value of an one-sided left tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (5)$$

⁴³Kim HY. Statistical notes for clinical researchers: Chi-squared test and Fisher's exact test. *Restor Dent Endod.* 2017 May;42(2):152-155. doi: 10.5395/rde.2017.42.2.152. Epub 2017 Mar 30. PMID: 28503482; PMCID: PMC5426219.

2.2.6. The Chi-square goodness of fit test

The χ^2 distribution is one of the most versatile distributions in applied statistics. Historically, the χ^2 distribution has been described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert (see [Helmert, 1876](#)). Later, the χ^2 distribution has been rediscovered by Karl Pearson (see [Pearson, 1900](#)) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The Chi-square goodness of fit test checks the agreement or conformity or consistency between a hypothetical or a theoretical distribution given in a population and a sample distribution drawn from such a population. Karl Pearson's approximate formula for calculating a Chi-square statistic may be shown schematically as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{(\text{Observed}_t - E(\text{Observed}_t))^2}{E(\text{Observed}_t)} \quad (6)$$

Some author prefer the use of Yate's correction for continuity (see [Yates, 1934](#)) when there is one degree of freedom.

Example

Let us illustrate the Chi-square goodness of fit test by an example. A random sample of 100 people with 44 men and 56 women is drawn from a certain population. It is assumed that men and women are equal in frequency in the population. The theoretical frequencies of 50 men and 50 women is compared with the observed number of men and women.

Bernoulli trial t	Event	Observed O_t	Expected $E(O_t)$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2 / E(O_t)$
1	Men	44	50	36	0.72
2	Women	56	50	36	0.72
Rows = 2		Sample size =	100	Chi-square =	1.44

There are rows - 1 = 2 - 1 = 1 degree of freedom and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A $\chi^2 = 1.44$ is less than 3.84 and not significant. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis: the sample distribution is consistent with a theoretical distribution given in population. In other words, men and women are more or less equal in frequency in the population. In the case of a necessary condition relationship (SINE), our hypotheses could be:

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) \geq 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

However, a probability cannot be greater than 1. Therefore, the hypotheses are more precisely

$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) = 1$ vs. $H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$

Accepting H_0 is equivalent with rejecting H_A and vice versa. Accepting H_A is equivalent with rejecting H_0 . Assumed that the degree of freedom is 1 and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A χ^2 of a necessary condition relationship which is less than 3.84 is not significant. Therefore, we would have to accept the null hypothesis: a sample distribution would be consistent with a theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship given in population. However, Chi-square like any statistics has its limitations. The Chi-square is highly sensitive to sample size. The Chi-square goodness of fit test might give inaccurate results when the sample size is too small ($N < 50$) or too large (see [Bagozzi, 1981](#)) (G-square test). When the sample sizes are too small, Fisher's exact test of independence can be considered too.

2.2.7. The P Value of extreme events

There are circumstances where N Bernoulli trials (see [Uspensky, 1937](#), p. 45) are performed while an event X_t should occur at each single Bernoulli trial t . The probability of a single event is given as

$$p(X_t) = p(X_t) = \frac{X_t}{X_t} \times p(X_t) = \frac{(X_t \times p(X_t))}{X_t} = \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} \quad (7)$$

The probability of a single anti-event or non-event et cetera is given as

$$p(\underline{X}_t) = 1 - p(X_t) = 1 - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t}{X_t} - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - X_t \times p(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{X_t} = \frac{E(\underline{X}_t)}{X_t} \quad (8)$$

As soon, as the number of Bernoulli trials increases, the probability of a single event follows approximately (see [Barukčić, 2019c](#), p. 1844) as

$$p(X_t) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(\underline{X}_t)}{N}\right)\right) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{N}\right)\right) \quad (9)$$

Under conditions where $X_t = N$, equation 9 simplifies to

$$p(X_t) = \exp(-(1 - p(X_t))) \quad (10)$$

There are single events or relationships where the probability of an event or of a relationship is constant from trial to trial and equals $p(X_t) = 1$ in the population. Nonetheless, for many reasons, such extreme events like the necessary condition relationship, the sufficient condition relationship, the exclusion relationship et cetera does not necessarily have to be given in a sample drawn from a population too. Under these circumstances, there is a need to proof whether there is a significant difference between the sample probability or proportion and the population probability or proportion or is the difference due to chance. In other words, does the sample probability or proportion deviate significantly from the population probability or proportion which itself is equal to 1. We perform a one-sided left tailed statistical test. A probability of a single event cannot be greater than 1, therefore our hypotheses are:

$H_0: p(X_t) \leq 0.999\ 999 \dots$ vs. $H_A: p(X_t) > 0.999\ 999 \dots$

In general, the expectation value of extreme events or relationship with $p(X_t) = 1$ at every single Bernoulli trial t is $E(X) = N \times p(X_t) = N \times 1 = N$. Thus far, under circumstances where $N = E(X)$, the hypotheses before simplify to

$$H_0: E(X) \leq N-1 \text{ vs. } H_A: E(X) > N-1$$

However, it is to be noted that $N > N-1$. The cumulative distribution function is given as

$$p(E(X_t))\text{cdf} = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots p(X_t = (N - 1)) + p(X_t = N) = +1 \quad (11)$$

It is

$$p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots p(X_t = (N - 1)) \quad (12)$$

and

$$p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = p(E(X_t) = N) \quad (13)$$

The P Value of a one-sided left (see [Barukčić, 2019c](#), p. 1846) tailed statistical test is given as

$$\text{P Value}_{\text{one sided left tailed}} = p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = 1 - p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(X_t)}{N}\right)\right) \quad (14)$$

We have reasons to believe that a left tailed P Value which is greater than or equal to the significance level α or P Value $\geq \alpha$, is providing some evidence to accept the null hypothesis: The sample distribution deviates significantly from the population distribution. Under such circumstances, the sample data would not support a claim that i.e. there is a significant *conditio sine qua non* relationship or *conditio per quam* relationship or exclusion relationship et cetera. However, a left tailed P Value which is less than the significance level α or P Value $< \alpha$, urges us to reject the null hypothesis and to accept the alternative hypothesis. In other words, there is no deviation of the probability found in a sample distribution from the the probability of a population distribution. It is $p(X_t) = 1$ with a certain P Value.

2.2.8. Bonferroni correction

Multiple testing at a certain level of significance α might amplify the probability of false-positive findings. In other words, the more inferences are made (on a certain data body i. e. subgroup analyses et cetera), the more likely erroneous inferences might realise. At the end, several independent or dependent statistical tests performed simultaneously (on the same data body) can induce the so called family-wise error rate (FWER) or multiple testing problem. The family-wise error rate or multiple testing problem (see [Tukey, 1994](#)) is ascribed to John Wilder Tukey (1915 – 2000), an American mathematician and statistician. The probability that at least one null hypothesis out of k null hypotheses tested is falsely rejected is no longer equal to the overall significance level α but equal to

$$\alpha_{\text{FWER}} = 1 - (1 - \alpha)^k \quad (15)$$

As a consequence, a higher significance threshold for an individual hypothesis, denoted as α_i , is demanded. Various statistical techniques have been developed to address this problem. The Bonferroni

multiple-comparison correction (see [Bonferroni, 1936](#); [Dunn, 1961](#)) is one of the solutions proposed to compensate for the number of inferences being made.

Example

An investigation is testing $m = 20$ hypotheses with a desired $\alpha = 0.05$. Under these circumstances, the Bonferroni correction might be of appropriate use. Each individual hypothesis should be tested at a single level of significance α_i given as

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\alpha}{m} = \frac{0,05}{20} = 0,0025 \quad (16)$$

where m is the total number hypotheses tested and α is the overall significance level. By requiring a stricter significance threshold, **an inflation of false positive results** can be prevented. In the context of further scientific development, there have been several trials to improve the Bonferroni method. One of these attempts is the so called Rom's Method published 1990 by Rom (see [Rom, 1990](#)) himself.

2.2.9. Bias

Many times, potential publication bias among the studies is assessed by Begg's funnel plot ⁴⁴, ⁴⁵, ⁴⁶, ⁴⁷ with something like a treatment effect (horizontal axis) and some measure of weight (inverse variance, standard error, sample size et cetera) on the vertical axis. It is not always an easy task to bring various studies together which differ in different aspects in order to re-analyse the same or for doing a meta-analysis. Due to several reasons, variability in the data of the studies and other difference might be found. These days the heterogeneity among the studies is assessed through a so called I^2 statistics ⁴⁸, ⁴⁹, ⁵⁰ to. Under usual circumstances, an I^2 value of 25%, 50% and 75% are regarded as low, moderate and high heterogeneity⁵¹. In this investigation, we preferred to control the study (design) bias and the heterogeneity among the studies by IOI, the index of independence ([Barukčić, 2019a](#)) and by IOU, the index of unfairness ([Barukčić, 2019b](#)).

⁴⁴Light RJ, Pillemer DB. Summing up. The science of reviewing research. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1984.

⁴⁵Egger M, Davey Smith G, Schneider M, Minder C. Bias in meta-analysis detected by a simple, graphical test. *BMJ*. 1997 Sep 13;315(7109):629-34. doi: 10.1136/bmj.315.7109.629. PMID: 9310563; PMCID: PMC2127453.

⁴⁶Begg CB, Mazumdar M. Operating characteristics of a rank correlation test for publication bias. *Biometrics*. 1994 Dec;50(4):1088-101. PMID: 7786990.

⁴⁷Lau J, Ioannidis JP, Terrin N, Schmid CH, Olkin I. The case of the misleading funnel plot. *BMJ*. 2006 Sep 16;333(7568):597-600. doi: 10.1136/bmj.333.7568.597. PMID: 16974018; PMCID: PMC1570006.

⁴⁸Cochran WG. The combination of estimates from different experiments. *Biometrics* 1954; 10(1): 101-29.

⁴⁹Higgins JP, Thompson SG. Quantifying heterogeneity in a meta-analysis. *Stat Med*. 2002 Jun 15;21(11):1539-58. doi: 10.1002/sim.1186. PMID: 12111919.

⁵⁰Higgins JP, Thompson SG, Deeks JJ, Altman DG. Measuring inconsistency in meta-analyses. *BMJ*. 2003 Sep 6;327(7414):557-60. doi: 10.1136/bmj.327.7414.557. PMID: 12958120; PMCID: PMC192859.

⁵¹Higgins JP, Thompson SG, Deeks JJ, Altman DG. Measuring inconsistency in meta-analyses. *BMJ*. 2003 Sep 6;327(7414):557-60. doi: 10.1136/bmj.327.7414.557. PMID: 12958120; PMCID: PMC192859.

3. Results

3.1. *Without being married, no ovarian cancer*

Under certain social or cultural circumstances (i.e. no sexual relationship before marriage or no extramarital intercourse), marital status is a possible, slight indicator of sexually transmitted diseases, including cancer too.

Theorem 1 (Without being married, no ovarian cancer).

Null-hypothesis (H_0):

Without being married, no ovarian cancer is true.

Alternative-hypothesis (H_A):

*Without being married, no ovarian cancer is **not** true.*

Proof by experiment/induction. Various studies investigated the relationship between marital status and cancer. The data ⁵², ⁵³ considered for re-analyses (see table 1 and table 2) provided some evidence to accept that the Null-hypothesis:

Without being married, **no** ovarian cancer is true (P Value (SINE) = 0,00043065).

□

⁵²Kato I, Tominaga S, Terao C. An epidemiological study on marital status and cancer incidence. *Jpn J Cancer Res.* 1989 Apr;80(4):306-11. doi: 10.1111/j.1349-7006.1989.tb02311.x. PMID: 2501246; PMCID: PMC5917738.

⁵³Fortner RT, Terry KL, Bender N, Brenner N, Hufnagel K, Butt J, Waterboer T, Tworoger SS. Sexually transmitted infections and risk of epithelial ovarian cancer: results from the Nurses' Health Studies. *Br J Cancer.* 2019 Apr;120(8):855-860. doi: 10.1038/s41416-019-0422-9. Epub 2019 Mar 21. PMID: 30894687; PMCID: PMC6474309.

3.2. Human papillomavirus is a cause of ovarian cancer

Theorem 2 (Human papillomavirus is a cause of ovarian cancer).

Null-hypothesis (H_0):

No causal relationship between human papillomavirus and ovarian cancer is true.

Alternative-hypothesis (H_A):

Causal relationship between human papillomavirus and ovarian cancer is true.

Proof by experiment/induction. Various studies investigated the relationship between HPV and OC with contradictory results. Nonetheless, view studies were able to provide a more or less convincing evidence of the relationship between HPV and OC (see table 4 and table 6 and table 7). Wu et al. (China, 2003; see table 4) convincingly demonstrated that HPV is a sufficient condition of OC (P Value (one-sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,0000193) while the causal relationship k has been highly significant and positive. Paradowska et al. (Poland, 2019; see table 6) provided evidence that HPV is a sufficient condition of OC (P Value (one-sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00576130). Last, but not least, Shokouh et al. (Iran, 2020; see table 7) provided very convincing, PCR based evidence that HPV is a sufficient condition of OC (P Value = 0,0) while the causal relationship has been highly significant (P Value (one-sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00081704) and positive ($k = +0,29330771$). Taking all together, we have some slight reason to accept the alternative hypothesis. HPV is a cause of OC (P Value (one-sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00081704).

□

3.3. Statins protect against ovarian cancer

Theorem 3 (The use of statins excludes ovarian cancer).

Null-hypothesis (H_0):

*An intake of statins **excludes** ovarian cancer is true.*

Alternative-hypothesis (H_A):

*An intake of statins **does not exclude** ovarian cancer is true.*

Proof by experiment/induction. Baandrup et al. ⁵⁴ provided very convincing evidence of the exclusion relationship between statin therapy and ovarian cancer (see table 8). An ever use of statins excludes ovarian cancer (p (EXCL) = 0,99309016; P Value (EXCL) = 0,0068860; Causal relationship $k = -0,00317135$) very effectively. This position is supported by the data of Akinwunmi et al. ⁵⁵ (see table 11). We accept the Null-hypothesis: An intake of statins excludes ovarian cancer (P Value (EXCL) = 0,0068860).

□

⁵⁴Baandrup L, Dehlendorff C, Friis S, Olsen JH, Kjær SK. Statin use and risk for ovarian cancer: a Danish nationwide case-control study. *Br J Cancer*. 2015 Jan 6;112(1):157-61. doi: 10.1038/bjc.2014.574. Epub 2014 Nov 13. PMID: 25393364; PMCID: PMC4453615.

⁵⁵Akinwunmi B, Vitonis AF, Titus L, Terry KL, Cramer DW. Statin therapy and association with ovarian cancer risk in the New England Case Control (NEC) study. *Int J Cancer*. 2019 Mar 1;144(5):991-1000. doi: 10.1002/ijc.31758. Epub 2018 Oct 30. PMID: 30006925; PMCID: PMC6320710.

4. Discussion

It is very remarkable and at the same time gratifying that the well-tolerated statins are very likely to be effective against ovarian cancer (see table 8 and table 9 and 10). This efficacy of statins against ovarian cancer allow us to ask a few more questions. Statins as competitive inhibitors of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-coenzyme A (HMG-CoA) reductase have secured anti-tumoral effects on multiple cancer types. Statins possess the property to inhibit the proliferation and induce cell death of human papilloma virus positive cells.⁵⁶,⁵⁷ For this reason, statins should be effective against prostate cancer⁵⁸, cervical cancer⁵⁹ and so on. Human papillomavirus itself is a small double-stranded deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) virus. Meanwhile, more than 170 types of HPV have been identified.⁶⁰ Usually, HPV genotypes are divided into two groups, oncogenic HPV genotypes (HPV types like 16, 18, 31, 33, 35, 39, 45, 51, 52, 56, 58, 59, 66 and 68)⁶¹,⁶² and non-oncogenic HPV genotypes⁶³. The relationship between HPV and ovarian cancer itself is heavily suspected and discussed in literature. Kaufman et al.⁶⁴ using southern blot hybridization reported 1987 that 10 out of 12 patients with advanced epithelial ovarian adenocarcinoma contained DNA of human papillomavirus type 6 (HPV-6). However, the authors retracted⁶⁵ 1 year later⁶⁶ this article. Other researchers employing polymerase chain reaction (PCR) techniques and using different oligonucleotide were not able to detect HPV DNA in ovarian carcinoma tissues.⁶⁷ In the further course of research numerous, very different studies

⁵⁶Crescencio ME, Rodríguez E, Páez A, Masso FA, Montañó LF, López-Marure R. Statins inhibit the proliferation and induce cell death of human papilloma virus positive and negative cervical cancer cells. *Int J Biomed Sci.* 2009 Dec;5(4):411-20. PMID: 23675166; PMCID: PMC3614803.

⁵⁷Sheng B, Song Y, Zhang J, Li R, Wang Z, Zhu X. Atorvastatin suppresses the progression of cervical cancer via regulation of autophagy. *Am J Transl Res.* 2020 Sep 15;12(9):5252-5268. PMID: 33042417; PMCID: PMC7540084.

⁵⁸Barukčić I. Human papillomavirus is the cause of human prostate cancer. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics* . 20 Aug.2019;9(4-s):577-88. Available from: <https://jddtonline.info/index.php/jddt/article/view/3385>

⁵⁹Barukčić, I. (2018) Human Papillomavirus—The Cause of Human Cervical Cancer. *Journal of Biosciences and Medicines*, 6, 106-125. doi: 10.4236/jbm.2018.64009

⁶⁰Sabatini ME, Chiocca S. Human papillomavirus as a driver of head and neck cancers. *Br J Cancer.* 2020 Feb;122(3):306-314. doi: 10.1038/s41416-019-0602-7. Epub 2019 Nov 11. PMID: 31708575; PMCID: PMC7000688.

⁶¹Niyazi M, Husaiyin S, Han L, Mamat H, Husaiyin K, Wang L. Prevalence of and risk factors for high-risk human papillomavirus infection: a population-based study from Hetian, Xinjiang, China. *Bosn J Basic Med Sci.* 2016 Jan 1;16(1):46-51. doi: 10.17305/bjbm.2016.593. PMID: 26773182; PMCID: PMC4765939.

⁶²Zeng Z, Austin RM, He X, et al. Prevalence of high-risk human papillomavirus infection in China: Analysis of 671,163 human papillomavirus test results from China's largest college of American pathologists-certified laboratory. *Am J Clin Pathol.* 2016;145:622-5

⁶³Castellsagué X, Bosch FX, Muñoz N. Environmental co-factors in HPV carcinogenesis. *Virus Res.* 2002 Nov;89(2):191-9. doi: 10.1016/s0168-1702(02)00188-0. PMID: 12445659.

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provided additional evidence of the relationship between HPV infection and ovarian cancer.⁶⁸,⁶⁹,⁷⁰,⁷¹ But at the bottom line, it is necessary to recognise that the currently available research results on this controversial issue are very contradictory⁷² and the relationship between HPV and OC is still less clear.⁷³,⁷⁴,⁷⁵,⁷⁶ A very wide variation in the prevalence of HPV in ovarian cancer is published by various studies.⁷⁷,⁷⁸ However, where does such enormous and wide variation between study results come about? Theoretically, there are several sources of bias. The technique used to detect HPV DNA is one of those sources.⁷⁹,⁸⁰,⁸¹ The type of specimen utilized (Formalin-Fixed Paraffin-Embedded (FPPE) tissues, frozen or and fresh tissues) has an impact on the quality of data too. The specific primers utilised to identify HPV are potentially not appropriate enough, et cetera.

In this study, it was possible to prove that the marital status is a necessary condition of ovarian cancer (see table 1 and table 2). However, regardless of marriage and family, the transmission of a potentially infectious agent as the cause of ovarian cancer through the air is very unlikely, since in

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⁷⁶Alavi G, Sharifi N, Sadeghian A, et al. Failure to demonstrate the role of high risk human papilloma virus in epithelial ovarian cancer. *Iran J Pathol.* 2012;7:151-6.

⁷⁷Cherif S, Amine A, Thies S, Taube ET, Braicu EI, Sehoul J, Kaufmann AM. Prevalence of human papillomavirus detection in ovarian cancer: a meta-analysis. *Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis.* 2021 Sep;40(9):1791-1802. doi: 10.1007/s10096-021-04282-7. Epub 2021 Jun 4. PMID: 34086102; PMCID: PMC8346400.

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this case other members of a family would also have to suffer from ovarian cancer (e.g. children) too. In point of fact, none detectable and reproducible evidence could be provided in this regard. To put it in a nutshell, we have every conceivable logical reason to assume that the nearness and intimacy in marriage is causally related to the development of ovarian carcinoma. However, this does not preclude that those who have multiple extra-marital sexual partners and/or frequent extra-marital sexual intercourse are not at very high risk for acquiring even more HPV subtypes. With all this in mind, it is necessary to point out those studies that could provide clear evidence of the relationship between HPV and OC (see table 4 and table 5 and table 6 and table 7). The results as provided by these studies are of course not sufficient to establish causality between HPV and OC. Nonetheless, these results cannot be treated as pure coincidence either. Especially, Shokouh et al. were able to provide clear evidence that HPV is a sufficient condition of OC (see table 7). Based on the data of Paradowska et al. (see table 6), it is necessary to consider a cause effect relationship between HPV and OC. In point of fact, even if the evidence presented by this publication is very convincing, further and more detailed studies are necessary to confirm these findings at the end. For numerous reasons and as exemplary for other investigations, it seems useful and worthy of consideration to standardize and to coordinate the worldwide research on HPV.

5. Conclusion

In a matter as weighty as this it is highly probable that within HPV, the cause of OC has been found. Nonetheless, for however one might try to twist the facts

‘statins are very effective against ovarian cancer.’

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals

on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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